

Big Data Workflows: Locality-aware Orchestration using Software Containers

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Abstract: The emergence of the Edge computing paradigm has shifted data processing from centralised infrastructures to heterogeneous and geographically distributed infrastructures. Therefore, data processing solutions must consider data locality to reduce the performance penalties from data transfers among remote data centres. Existing Big Data processing solutions provide limited support for handling data locality and are inefficient in processing small and frequent events specific to the Edge environments. This article proposes a novel architecture and a proof-of-concept implementation for software container-centric Big Data workflow orchestration that puts data locality at the forefront. The proposed solution considers the available data locality information, leverages long-lived containers to execute workflow steps, and handles the interaction with different data sources through containers. We compare the proposed solution with Argo Workflows and demonstrate a significant performance improvement in the execution speed for processing the same data units. Finally, we carry out experiments with the proposed solution under different configurations and analyze individual aspects affecting the performance of the overall solution.

Keywords: Big Data workflows; orchestration; data locality; software containers

1. Introduction

In recent years, harnessing large data sets from various sources has become a pillar of rapid innovation for many domains such as marketing, finance, agriculture, and healthcare [1]. The Big Data domain has evolved rapidly, and new challenges have arisen at different levels of the technological stack, from the complex business logic to the infrastructure required to process the ever-increasing volume, velocity, and variety of data. Working with Big Data is a complex process involving collaboration among a wide range of specialisations (such as distributed systems, data science, and business domain expertise) [2–4]. Handling such complexity naturally comes with an increased cost, and the value extracted from the data must, thereby, offset this cost.

Big Data workflows formalise and automate the processes that data goes through to produce value by providing necessary abstractions for defining workflows and efficiently leveraging underlying hardware resources. In the context of Big Data workflows, we consider computing resources, such as processors (CPUs), memory, and storage, as relevant hardware resources (from now on referred to as just resources) among others, e.g., [5,6]. Big Data workflows usually integrate various data sets and leverage different programming languages or technologies to process data. Therefore, a desirable feature of a Big Data workflow system is to orchestrate workflows in a technology-agnostic manner, both in terms of data integration and processing logic. Accordingly, approaches based on software containers have emerged to create and execute workflows using processing steps in line with these considerations. While it is beneficial to leverage

Citation: Lastname, F.; Lastname, F.; Lastname, F. Title. *Sensors* **2021**, *1*, 0. <https://doi.org/>

Received:

Accepted:

Published:

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

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36 software containers, packaging and isolating applications for deployment, to better
37 separate concerns in a Big Data workflow system, higher-level abstractions come with a
38 performance penalty; thus, it becomes more relevant to ensure the system performs as
39 efficiently as possible.

40 Traditionally, Cloud service providers have been the standard solution for working
41 with Big Data. However, Cloud services are inherently centralised in a small number
42 of locations (i.e., data centres) worldwide. Moreover, with the advent of the Internet
43 of Things (IoT), significant amounts of data are generated at Edge networks [7]. With
44 the data processing happening on geographically distributed systems across Edge and
45 Cloud resources, reducing the delay and cost of transferring data over the network
46 becomes crucial. Transferring massive amounts of data to the Cloud is expensive and
47 may incur latency, making low-latency scenarios unfeasible. To address these issues, the
48 Edge computing paradigm [8] aims to complement Cloud Computing by leveraging
49 hardware resources situated closer to the Edge of the network to offload processing,
50 reduce transfer cost, and satisfy the latency requirements. However, existing solutions
51 are mainly designed for Cloud-only workloads, making them unsuitable or inefficient
52 for workloads spanning both the Cloud and Edge. In this context, in order to alleviate
53 the aforementioned problems, this article addresses the following research questions:

- 54 • How can data locality be implicitly integrated with container-centric Big Data
55 workflow orchestration?
- 56 • How can software containers be used to facilitate the interaction with different data
57 management systems as part of Big Data workflows?
- 58 • How can containers encapsulating processing logic be used to improve the perfor-
59 mance of Big Data workflows?

60 To this end, we propose a novel architecture for container-centric Big Data workflow
61 orchestration systems that makes containerised Big Data workflow systems more efficient
62 on Cloud and Edge resources [9]. Our proposed approach considers (i) data locality, (ii)
63 leverages long-lived containers (i.e., containers whose life-cycle is not tied to a particular
64 data unit) to execute workflow steps, and (iii) handles the interaction with different
65 data sources through containers. We compare our proposed approach with a similar
66 existing solution, Argo workflows. The comparison shows that by considering data
67 locality, our proposed approach significantly improves the performance in terms of data
68 processing speed (up to five times better). We also present a set of experiments with
69 different configurations analysing individual aspects affecting the performance of the
70 overall solution.

71 The rest of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 gives the relevant context.
72 Section 3 provides an analysis of the problem. Section 4 discusses related work. Section
73 5 presents the proposed solution and Section 6 describes its implementation. Finally,
74 Section 7 provides experimental evaluation of the proposed solution, and Section 8
75 concludes the article and outlines future work.

76 2. Background

77 Big Data has quickly gained momentum as it allows the exploitation of data to
78 uncover hidden trends that give valuable insights that drive business decisions and
79 support research (e.g., [10,11]). Big Data solutions have been successfully leveraged
80 in a large number of industries. The general applicability of Big Data patterns stems
81 from the fact that many real-world phenomena can be better understood and predicted
82 given sufficient data. The characteristics, e.g., volume, velocity, and variety of Big Data,
83 translate into challenges at all levels of the technology stack for Big Data processing:

- 84 1. At the **infrastructure level**, significant raw network, storage, memory, and process-
85 ing resources are required to handle Big Data. Often these resources are provided
86 by multiple machines, organised in a distributed system.

Figure 1. Workflow as sequence of steps with communication mediums.

- 87 2. At the **platform level**, software frameworks that can effectively leverage the avail-
 88 able resources and handle the ever-changing needs of Big Data operations need to
 89 be continuously developed.
- 90 3. At the **application level**, algorithms running on the previously mentioned plat-
 91 forms need to be devised and combined to extract value from the data. Applications
 92 can also facilitate the interaction with a Big Data solution (e.g., visualisation tools
 93 used by business executives to analyse the results produced by the solution).

94 Devising algorithms and tools that help process and extract value from the data
 95 further amplify the complexity and cost of building comprehensive Big Data solutions.
 96 Consequently, another V, the **value** the solution generates, which needs to offset the high
 97 cost, is often included as a central characteristic of Big Data.

98 2.1. Big Data Workflows

99 Raw data must be taken through a series of operations (e.g., cleaning, aggregation,
 100 and transformation) before producing valuable insights. While it is possible for each of
 101 these steps to be manually triggered and independently controlled in an ad-hoc manner,
 102 workflow orchestration tools facilitate the automation of the execution and sequencing
 103 of these operations, allowing reliable and reproducible execution of complex processes.
 104 Key concepts used in workflow orchestration [12] (see Figure 1) include:

- 105 • **Step:** Steps are the atomic units upon which workflows are defined. A step encaps-
 106 ulates business logic units that receive data as input from a data source, processes
 107 them, and then pushes the outputs to a data sink.
- 108 • **Workflow:** Individual steps can be linked together to form a workflow. A workflow
 109 is a linear sequence of steps with the semantics of executing the steps. Big Data
 110 workflows are specified in more complex configurations. A widely used model
 111 stems from graph theory, which describes a workflow as a directed acyclic graph
 112 (DAG).
- 113 • **Data communication medium:** The distributed nature of Big Data processing war-
 114 rants the existence of a data communication medium through which information
 115 can be exchanged between the components of the system. Thereby, both the inputs
 116 and the outputs of a step connect to such channels.
- 117 • **Control flow communication medium:** To be able to execute the workflows, con-
 118 trol messages (e.g., triggering a step, notifying when a step has finished) have to
 119 be exchanged within the system through a control flow communication medium.
 120 Examples of such communication mediums include point-to-point network com-
 121 munication between components and message queues.

122 Creating Big Data workflows is a complex process involving knowledge from mul-
123 tiple domains (hardware provisioning, cluster management, data handling, different
124 processing steps, definition of workflows according to business needs, and orchestra-
125 tion). Delegating the different responsibilities to independent components allows easier
126 development of both the orchestration frameworks and the workflows running on top
127 of them, reducing the costs and making Big Data workflows more accessible.

128 2.2. *Cloud and Edge Computing*

129 Cloud Computing paves the way for accessible, affordable, and efficient Big Data
130 processing through scalable, elastic, and “pay-per-use” models. Cloud deployments are
131 best suited for cases where the producer of data is mainly centralised. However, with
132 the advancement of Ubiquitous Computing, tremendous amounts of data are produced
133 by devices (e.g., sensors, personal devices, and vehicles) at the Edge of the network.
134 With the number of such devices increasing rapidly, the traditional model for using
135 centralised Cloud resources becomes unfeasible. Edge Computing [13] complements
136 Cloud Computing by performing computations on resources physically located closer
137 to the Edge of the networks. In this respect, **Computing Continuum** [14] refers to all
138 available resources for a system, from the Edge of the network to the Cloud.

139 Although the Edge Computing paradigm addresses some fundamental limitations
140 of Cloud Computing, it also faces a different set of challenges [15]. Among others, these
141 notably include:

- 142 • Hardware resources on Edge devices exhibit different characteristics and capabil-
143 ities compared to Cloud resources (e.g., processor architectures, processor clock
144 speeds, and amounts of memory). Therefore, software running on such devices
145 has to be designed to consider these resource constraints. At the same time, Edge
146 deployments offer limited or no elasticity.
- 147 • Edge resources are geographically distributed, and the latencies can differ signifi-
148 cantly depending on the distance between the communicating parties.
- 149 • Geographical distribution also raises logistical challenges, as these devices can be
150 spread over wide areas and sometimes even in hard-to-reach locations, making
151 provisioning and maintenance a significant challenge.
- 152 • The nature of Edge resources also makes them prone to failures at the device
153 level (hardware failures) or supporting infrastructure (network failures). Software
154 solutions targeting Edge deployments need to tolerate failures gracefully and, if
155 possible, operate offline for extended periods.
- 156 • Security and privacy are two complex domains where Edge Computing plays a
157 significant role. On the one hand, processing data closer to the source can make
158 it easier to adhere to a certain jurisdiction and ensure better security and privacy.
159 On the other hand, large-scale Edge deployments are inherently more complicated
160 to secure, mainly due to their geographical spread, and the risk of having devices
161 compromised through physical interference is much higher than in a Cloud-only
162 setup.

163 2.3. *Software Containers and Big Data*

164 Software containers are standardised, isolated units of software that package every-
165 thing required to run an application¹. They provide a lightweight and faster virtualisa-
166 tion alternative to hypervisor virtualisation [16,17]. Software containers exhibit a series
167 of characteristics that make them applicable to a wide range of domains:

- 168 • Containers ensure the packaged software runs in complete isolation from other
169 applications on the same operating system. Packaging all dependencies in a con-
170 tainer can avoid challenging issues such as conflicting dependencies and complex
171 prerequisite configurations.

¹ <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container>

- 172 • The low overhead introduced by containers allows many containers to be run
173 efficiently on a single node, making them a good fit for resource-constrained envi-
174 ronments.
- 175 • Software that can run in a container is not limited to a particular technology or
176 programming language, allowing solutions leveraging software containers to or-
177 chestrate cooperation of components developed using different technologies easily.
- 178 • Containers are a widely adopted standard for software packaging, which translates
179 into two major benefits. First, containerised software is easier to share and reuse
180 across different environments. Second, containers can be used to move the execution
181 of logic onto a distributed system's nodes ("function shipping").

182 Container orchestration solutions, such as Kubernetes², simplify the deployment
183 and management of highly distributed systems by creating abstractions for the un-
184 derlying infrastructure and facilitating the interaction between the components of an
185 application. Software containers are extensively leveraged in Cloud environments [18],
186 and in some cases, containerised applications are referred to as Cloud-native applica-
187 tions [19]. Several works also identify software containers as a feasible technology for
188 resource-constrained Edge environments [20–22]. In the context of Big Data, containers
189 have been used to simplify the deployment and management of entire Big Data solutions
190 or individual components. Leveraging containers in Big Data solutions can also lead
191 to performance improvements when compared to the hypervisor-based virtualisation
192 alternatives [23].

193 There is a distinction between the two strategies of using containers in Big Data
194 solutions at a high level. First, software containers are leveraged to deploy and manage
195 the components of a Big Data processing platform. Although this approach simplifies the
196 deployment process, it does not influence the run-time aspects of the platform. Second,
197 software containers are used as an integral part of the architecture and as a mechanism
198 through which custom behaviour can be injected into the platform (e.g., data processing
199 logic). Software containers have gained much traction in the field of microservices
200 as they greatly simplify the management of highly distributed systems [24,25]. Such
201 an architecture can provide some benefits, including modularity, loose coupling, and
202 technology independence, which align with the needs of Big Data workflow systems.

203 3. Problem Analysis

204 The high velocity of the data, combined with the large volume, mandates the
205 processing to happen efficiently and cost-effectively to produce value that outweighs the
206 costs. Therefore, **execution time** and **bandwidth usage** are two indicators that are often
207 measured in Big Data systems and determine the feasibility of a given system. In the
208 following, we introduce the essential concepts and techniques to reduce the execution
209 time and bandwidth usage in Big Data workflows.

210 3.1. Data Locality

211 Data locality [26] refers to moving computation closer to the data, which is typically
212 cheaper and faster than moving data closer to the computation. The nature of working
213 with Big Data mandates the resources (e.g., network, memory, CPU, disk) of multiple
214 machines to be pooled together in a distributed system. A desirable characteristic
215 of distributed systems is to hide the complexities of the distributed resources behind
216 a single interface, such that the entire system appears as a single entity (e.g., Cloud
217 storage systems such as Amazon S3). However, it makes it more challenging to leverage
218 individual hosts comprising the distributed systems. For example, a fundamental
219 invariant of current computer architectures is that a CPU can only work with data
220 present in the memory of the same machine.

² <https://kubernetes.io/>

221 Consequently, the movement of data across machines becomes an integral part
222 of any Big Data system. With traditional communication protocols that rely on the
223 operating system network stack (e.g., TCP/IP-based protocols), latency becomes critical
224 for many use cases. To this end, more efficient protocols have emerged. For example,
225 RDMA (Remote Direct Memory Access) [27] is a protocol that allows the transfer of
226 data stored in the memory of one machine to another without involving the CPU or
227 the operating system kernel through specialised network cards. As the volume of data
228 is significant in the context of Big Data, the network traffic and the associated latency
229 of transferring data between machines can influence the overall cost and performance.
230 Even for solutions targeted at centralised deployment (such as Cloud deployments),
231 data locality has proven to be effective in reducing the cost and execution times [28,29].
232 For example, Apache Spark [30] leverages the information provided by the Hadoop File
233 System (HDFS) and knowledge about outputs of previous executions of jobs to minimise
234 the data transfer.

235 One of the core motivations of the Edge Computing paradigm is reducing the
236 amount of data transferred from the Edge of the network to the Cloud and supporting
237 lower latency scenarios, making data locality a primary concern for any Edge Computing
238 solution. However, data locality is only one aspect that can be considered when schedul-
239 ing data processing tasks. Other aspects such as load distribution and heterogeneity of
240 the available resources on different nodes need to be balanced together with data locality
241 to perform the tasks effectively [31]. There exist studies proposing advanced scheduling
242 strategies to balance the reduction of data transfer with load distribution (e.g., [32,33]).

243 3.2. *Inter-Component Communication Optimisation*

244 Separation of concerns and delegating responsibilities to different components have
245 numerous benefits; however, the communication between components may introduce
246 other performance and efficiency overhead due to message serialisation and transfer
247 through potentially slow mediums. For example, a simple method invocation in a
248 monolithic solution can be turned into a REST API call for a solution where components
249 are separated. The choice of communication protocols directly impacts the performance
250 and bandwidth utilisation, as different protocols provide different guarantees related to
251 data transmission (e.g., TCP ensures an ordered and lossless transmission but requires
252 multiple round trips to establish connections and exchange data, while UDP is faster but
253 less reliable).

254 Different protocols introduce additional overhead by injecting more data in trans-
255 mission packets (e.g., HTTP headers). Techniques, such as compression and binary
256 serialisation, help reduce the size of the payload. Furthermore, there exist studies
257 exploring the use of RDMA-backed memory channels to support fast and efficient
258 inter-container communication (e.g., [34]). Apart from the bandwidth utilisation and
259 speed of a particular protocol, the contract defining the communication between two
260 entities (message format, content, and semantics) plays a significant role in facilitating
261 the integration between components. Defining and enforcing a communication contract
262 between components allows decoupling them from one another.

263 3.3. *Lifecycle Management of Containers*

264 Software containers are a lightweight virtualisation alternative to traditional hypervisor-
265 based virtualisation; however, there is still a cost associated with starting up and shutting
266 down containers on demand. Life-cycle management has a high impact on workflow
267 execution time, and reusing containers to process multiple units of data (i.e., long-lived
268 containers) is a way to improve it [35]. For many use cases, the execution time of the work
269 delegated to a particular container is high, thus making the overhead of instantiating
270 containers negligible.

271 In Edge Computing environments, the available resources are limited, and less
272 data can be processed on a single host at a given point in time. Furthermore, with data

273 being constantly processed in small batches (or even streamed), there is a need for this
274 processing to happen as quickly as possible to achieve the desired throughput. In such
275 cases, the overhead of setting up and tearing down containers can quickly add up and
276 become a significant bottleneck for the solution's performance.

277 *3.4. Integration with Data Management Solutions*

278 One of the pillars of Big Data processing is to reason over and process heterogeneous
279 data sets together in a unified manner. These data sets can be stored using different
280 technologies, and the interaction with these technology requires complex logic in itself.
281 Thus, Big Data workflow systems should facilitate easy integration with different data
282 management solutions, such as databases, file systems, Cloud storage, and Web services.

283 **4. Related Work**

284 In this section, we first present and discuss the related work in terms of existing
285 published literature and then in terms of existing tools.

286 Regarding the published literature, Valerie et al. [36] discuss the effect of in-memory
287 processing and data locality on neuroimaging data sets and show the importance and
288 benefits of data locality. However, they do not propose any new system or orchestrator
289 tool and only evaluate the performance of existing systems. Ching et al. [37] propose
290 new techniques for implementing locality-aware virtual machines. They mainly focus on
291 improving the performance of MapReduce programs in heterogeneous and hybrid Cloud
292 environments and propose a technique to enhance data locality using a virtual machine
293 mapping technique. Thereby, the locality-aware technique balances workloads and
294 reduces communication overheads at run-time, but it is only restricted to MapReduce
295 applications. Therefore, it cannot be employed with the more general-purpose software
296 containers. August and Christoph [38] present a method of extending smart containers
297 for data locality-aware skeleton programming. They extend the existing SkePU skeleton
298 programming framework to enhance the performance of sequences of transformations
299 on smart containers. However, the framework does not provide support for orchestrating
300 workflows or container lifecycle management.

301 Bu et al. [39] describe a task scheduling technique for MapReduce applications
302 that minimizes interference while keeping task-data localization. The study, however,
303 disregards network effects, assuming that data flow between co-hosted virtual ma-
304 chines is equally efficient as local data access. Choi et al. [40] present a mechanism for
305 locality-aware resource management in High-Performance Computing (HPC) Cloud en-
306 vironments, called Data-Locality Aware Workflow Scheduling (D-LAWS). Their solution
307 condenses virtual machines and includes task parallelism through data flow into the
308 task execution planning of a data-intensive scientific process. However, they do not take
309 into account the role of software containers in scientific workflows.

310 Ahlehigh et al. [41] present a video-aware scheduling strategy that includes storing
311 video data in a macro-base station to boost video throughput and lessens the likelihood
312 of movies freezing. A heuristic approach to the storage allotment issue in macro-base
313 stations is presented by Gu et al. [42]. Small base stations may deliver better data rates
314 than macro-base stations since they are located closer to users. Finally, Vengadeswaran
315 and Balasundaram [43] propose an approach that also considers the data locality factor,
316 but it is limited to Hadoop. The default data placement strategy of Hadoop creates and
317 allocates blocks randomly across the cluster. To overcome this issue, they propose an
318 optimal data placement strategy to improve the performance of Big Data applications.
319 These methods focus on optimising data placement strategies rather than the real-time
320 migration of computing steps closer to the data.

321 In the following, we review existing orchestration tools selected according to the
322 following criteria: (i) ability to incorporate data locality in the orchestration process,
323 (ii) support for container lifecycle management, and (iii) the ease of integration with
324 data management solutions.

- 325 • Snakemake [44] is a workflow orchestration tool that supports wrapping individual
326 steps in containers, and different data solutions can be integrated into workflows by
327 extending the Snakemake codebase. However, there is no support for controlling
328 where the computation happens (data locality).
- 329 • Kubeflow³ is a workflow orchestration tool for machine learning-related workflows.
330 The only storage supported is Minio (a Cloud-native, open-source storage solution
331 implementing Amazon S3 Cloud storage protocol). It offers no support for data
332 locality.
- 333 • Makeflow [45] is a workflow orchestration tool that can orchestrate workflows on a
334 wide variety of infrastructures. However, it does not have any built-in support for
335 different data management systems or data locality features.
- 336 • Pachyderm⁴ is another machine learning workflow orchestration solution, but the
337 only storage system it supports is the Pachyderm file system, a distributed file
338 system built to provide supporting features to Pachyderm.
- 339 • Pegasus⁵ is a workflow orchestration solution that supports containerised steps
340 and leverages the location of the processed files to schedule the steps on the same
341 host. However, its data management is limited to using only file systems.
- 342 • Airflow⁶ is one of the most popular data workflow orchestrators that supports
343 the execution of the workflows on a Kubernetes cluster. It also controls where
344 instances of steps are created, but it should be set manually when the workflow is
345 defined, making it inefficient in dynamically-changing environments. It is possible
346 to integrate different data management solutions by extending the Airflow code
347 with providers, limiting it to Python implementations only.
- 348 • Argo Workflows⁷ is a workflow orchestration solution natively built on Kubernetes
349 and supports data locality through a set of mechanisms. Similar to the Airflow
350 solution, different data management solutions can be integrated but require ad-hoc
351 changes and integration with the Argo code libraries.

352 All of the considered solutions leverage short-lived containers as part of the orches-
353 tration – a container is created to execute work and destroyed as soon as the processing
354 completes because these solutions target primarily batch processing scenarios. In terms
355 of data locality specification, Argo offers the most expressive features as it leverages
356 the complete functional offering of Kubernetes. However, by default, the limitation of
357 having to specify data locality at workflow definition time (introduced with Airflow
358 analysis) applies to Argo. Argo offers a mechanism through which respective outputs of
359 processing steps can be used to modify the parameters (for data locality in this case) of
360 subsequent steps in the workflow, allowing for dynamic data locality configurations at
361 run-time. However, such an approach would require additional logic to be injected into
362 the processing step. Although limited in terms of data locality features, Pegasus does
363 handle data locality implicitly, without modifying the workflow definition. In contrast,
364 for both Argo and Airflow, while offering more expressive data locality features, the
365 workflow definition has to capture these details, thus breaking the separation of concerns
366 principle.

367 5. Proposed Solution

368 We propose an approach based on a workflow system architecture covering the
369 run-time considerations of Big Data workflows that take into account the separation of
370 concerns principle. The proposed architecture has three main layers:

3 <https://www.kubeflow.org>

4 <https://github.com/pachyderm/pachyderm>

5 <https://pegasus.isi.edu>

6 <https://airflow.apache.org>

7 <https://argoproj.github.io/projects/argo>

- 371 1. **Control layer:** It is responsible for the execution of workflows concerning their
 372 definitions (e.g., correct step sequencing and data being processed). The main
 373 component of the control layer is the **orchestrator**.
- 374 2. **Data layer:** It collectively refers to all the components involved in data handling
 375 (i.e., storage and retrieval of data, and moving data between hosts to make it
 376 available to compute steps that require it). The layer includes the **data store**
 377 component, referring to the technology used to store data (e.g., distributed file
 378 system and Cloud storage) and the **data adapter** component, serving as an interface
 379 between the data store and the other components in the workflow.
- 380 3. **Compute layer:** It refers to the processing logic contained in the steps used in the
 381 workflow. The compute layer is composed of multiple **compute steps**, and, in a
 382 sequence, they form a workflow. Additionally, the approach allows that multiple
 383 instances of the same compute step type run in parallel.

Figure 2. (a) Detailed view of a compute step, and (b) data locality as a multi-objective optimisation problem.

384 The components of the different layers can be spread across multiple hosts, and
 385 the orchestrator serves as the coordinator of the centralised architecture. Using a cen-
 386 tralised architecture is motivated by leveraging data locality when the execution of Big
 387 Data workflows requires knowledge about the entire system (e.g., component physical
 388 placement) and the data that flows through it (the physical location where data are
 389 stored). The centralised architecture greatly simplifies the acquisition, management, and
 390 usage of this information. Data are organised into discrete, indivisible, and independent
 391 units when passing through the system. These represent the units of work at both the
 392 orchestration level and individual step level. Each unit is processed independently, and
 393 multiple units can be processed in parallel across different steps. Handling the execu-
 394 tion of the workflow at the data unit level can improve the performance significantly
 395 compared to the models that execute steps synchronously (all outputs of the previous
 396 step have to be available to start the next one) [12,46].

397 Whenever a new unit of data is available in the system, the orchestrator is notified,
398 and it passes on the notification to a "compute step" for processing. The compute step
399 may produce one or more outputs from the input, each being a new data unit that
400 continues to flow through the system independently of the others. Organising the work
401 in independent units enables tasks to be distributed across all the available resources,
402 allowing the proposed solution to scale horizontally (increase the processing power by
403 adding more hosts in the distributed system). Figure 2 (a) depicts a high-level overview
404 of the three layers and their interactions. The following sections present each layer in
405 detail.

406 5.1. Control Layer

407 Upon receiving a notification indicating that new data are available to be processed,
408 the orchestrator needs to determine what type of compute step needs to invoke for the
409 current data unit, according to the workflow specification. For example, in a workflow
410 consisting of three sequential steps, the data units outputted by the second step need to
411 be passed to an instance of the third step. Throughout the system, there can be multiple
412 instances of the same compute step type. The orchestrator is responsible for choosing
413 one of the instances to process the data.

414 Instead of relying on traditional load balancing algorithms (such as round-robin,
415 random, and least connections), the orchestrator needs to employ a custom routing
416 decision algorithm that takes the number of variables as input. The orchestrator decides
417 about the routing based on available information, such as data locality, current load,
418 varying resource availability, cost, and existing policies (see Figure 2 (b)). This list
419 is not exhaustive and presents only a subset of potential aspects considered when
420 making a routing decision. Optimising cost and performance while ensuring all the
421 explicit requirements of the workflow are met makes the routing a complex, multivariate
422 optimisation problem, with no clear best decision where trade-off in one or more areas is
423 necessary.

424 To provide data locality, the orchestrator needs to know the physical location of
425 both the data to be processed and the possible target step instances and also a model
426 to calculate the distance between two locations. Moreover, the orchestrator needs
427 to continue operating when presented with unexpected, partial, or missing locality
428 data, as some data adapters may not provide granular data locality information. The
429 inputs to the routing decision need to be acquired and made available by the module
430 responsible for the decision. Depending on the volume and velocity of the units of data
431 flowing through the orchestrator, the calculation of the routing decision needs to be
432 efficient to avoid spending a significant amount of time routing each unit. This means
433 that some of the inputs may have to be pre-calculated or estimated asynchronously,
434 as acquiring information about all the possible targets synchronously may incur a
435 significant performance cost.

436 5.2. Data Layer

437 The ability to share data between the nodes hosting the compute step instances is a
438 fundamental requirement of the proposed solution. This allows the steps to pass data
439 from one another as part of the workflow execution. All the interactions with the data
440 storage happen through the data adapter in the proposed architecture, serving as an
441 intermediary between the data storage technology and the orchestration components.
442 The data adapter model hides the complexities and particularities of interacting with
443 the data storage by separating the logic into a dedicated component that exposes a
444 simplified interface for external communications. Separating data handling concerns
445 from the compute step creates a modular architecture that facilitates and encourages the
446 reusability of both components in multiple workflows. For example, a compute step
447 processing images can be used to process images from multiple data sources, and the
448 same data solution can be reused with different compute steps.

449 In addition to reusability, separating the compute steps from the data adapter allows
450 for more flexibility in terms of technologies chosen to implement either of them. For
451 example, a compute step can be implemented in Python while the data adapter in Java
452 and the two components can still communicate. Apart from interacting with the under-
453 lying storage, the data adapter is also responsible for providing the other components
454 in the system with information about the physical localisation of the data to support
455 locality-aware work scheduling. The data locality model employed to communicate the
456 localisation information needs to have the following characteristics:

- 457 1. It needs to apply to both the data units flowing through the system and the compute
458 step instances, as the information it captures is used to route data units to be
459 processed on compute step instances in proximity.
- 460 2. The localisation information needs to apply to resources throughout the Comput-
461 ing Continuum, and a distance measure needs to be determinable for any two
462 localisations.
- 463 3. The data locality model needs to be granular enough to capture host-level informa-
464 tion.
- 465 4. Different data storage solutions have different capabilities of exposing information
466 about where data are stored; thus, the data locality model should support reserved
467 values to indicate that parts of the information are missing.

468 5.3. *Compute Layer*

469 The compute steps follow a simple execution model since both the orchestration
470 and data handling logic are handled by external components:

- 471 1. A compute step is provided with a unit of data as input (provided by the data
472 adapter).
- 473 2. The processing logic is applied in the compute step.
- 474 3. The processing logic can produce one or more outputs, picked up by a data adapter,
475 resulting in notifications for the orchestrator.

476 This architecture gives complete freedom to execute any logic that can be run in
477 containers as the implementation of the compute step has no restrictions over what the
478 processing logic can do with the input data. Neither the input nor the output data are
479 typed.

480 5.4. *Extension Model*

481 A widely used model for building upon and extending a framework is integrat-
482 ing a software development kit (a set of language-specific libraries) that handles the
483 interaction between the features provided by the framework and the code extending or
484 building upon it (user logic). The communication between the two components then
485 happens via language-specific constructs, such as method invocations, and is backed by
486 the memory of the hosting process. With container technologies easing the management
487 and deployment of microservices, the framework functionality can be completely sepa-
488 rated from the user logic by being placed in a dedicated container. This container can
489 communicate with the user logic (presumably in another container) through an external
490 communication medium.

491 This approach provides better isolation of the two components and allows for
492 integration between different programming languages or frameworks, as the communi-
493 cation is agnostic to the used programming language. Even though the communication
494 medium (e.g., network calls, files, sockets) can be accessed by both components, a crucial
495 aspect is to ensure the communication protocol (e.g., HTTP, gRPC) is supported by
496 both ends. The current architecture opts for the container-based extension model as it
497 aligns better with the architecture requirements. The container-based extension model
498 becomes apparent when diving deeper into the architecture of a compute step (Figure
499 3). A compute step is logically composed of a **framework agent** and processing logic,
500 running in a separate container. The framework agent container is responsible for coor-

501 dinating the execution in the context of a single step (retrieving the input data, triggering
 502 the processing logic, handling the output data). It effectively hides the complexities
 503 related to the orchestration and acts as the intermediary between the data and compute
 504 components. Thus it allows them to have simplified interfaces they need to adhere to
 505 dedicated only to their function (handling data or processing it), as follows:

Figure 3. A detailed view of a compute step.

- 506 1. The framework agent needs to accept requests from the orchestrator to process a
- 507 unit of data.
- 508 2. Based on the instructions received from the orchestrator, it reaches out to the data
- 509 adapter to retrieve the input data.
- 510 3. Once the input data is accessible to the container hosting the processing logic, the
- 511 agent must send a request to trigger the computation.
- 512 4. The output data are passed to the data adapter and the orchestrator is notified that
- 513 new data have become available.

514 By leveraging the container-based extension model, the microservice-inspired archi-
 515 tecture combines the code contributed by the user (i.e., data adapter, business logic, and
 516 data store) and the framework provided components (i.e., orchestrator and framework
 517 agent) to define and execute workflows. By injecting two components implementing
 518 simple interfaces (one for data handling and one for processing logic), the framework
 519 can orchestrate the execution workflows composed of steps implemented in different
 520 programming languages or technologies and leverage different data storage solutions.
 521 The data handling and processing logic are completely separated, allowing them to
 522 be created and to evolve independently, thus helping with the separation of concerns
 523 between the stakeholders involved in creating workflows. The proposed architecture
 524 allows the framework users to inject data and processing logic into a workflow definition,
 525 combining the two elements.

526 6. Implementation

527 We implemented our proposed solution as a proof of concept using Docker and Ku-
 528 bernetes [16]. The code of our proposed solution, along with the associated Dockerfiles,
 529 and Kubernetes YAML files to deploy the model to Kubernetes clusters, are publicly
 530 available under the MIT license⁸.

531 Docker is used for building the container images for both the framework compo-
 532 nents (orchestrator and framework agent) and the examples of pluggable components
 533 (compute steps and data storage). The container images contain all the information
 534 needed by a container run-time to run the components. At run-time, the container
 535 orchestration solution uses the images to instantiate the different components as needed.
 536 Kubernetes was used to manage and orchestrate the deployment and communication

⁸ <https://github.com/alin-corodescu/MSc-workflows>

537 between the components. Kubernetes is the industry standard for container orchestra-
538 tion and exposes abstractions over the hardware resources it manages. Additionally, it is
539 tailored to work well in resource-constrained environments, such as Edge environments.

540 The following is a brief introduction to the main Kubernetes abstractions and
541 features referenced in the remainder article:

- 542 1. **Nodes:** These are the abstraction Kubernetes uses for the hosts making up a cluster.
543 These can either be physical or virtual machines.
- 544 2. **Pods:** These are the smallest units that Kubernetes manages and deploys. A pod
545 is a group of one or more containers, logically belonging together to perform a
546 particular task.
- 547 3. **Services:** These are a type of Kubernetes resource that helps connecting pods or
548 expose functionalities outside the cluster. A selection criterion is used to identify
549 the pods hosting the application the service exposes. The communication with the
550 service is done through a designated IP address and port, with the request routing
551 and load balancing between the pods being handled by Kubernetes.
- 552 4. **DaemonSets:** These enable Kubernetes users to deploy an instance of a pod to
553 every node in the cluster.
- 554 5. **Labels:** All Kubernetes resources can be associated with labels to help identify
555 and distinguish resources serving different purposes (e.g., pods hosting different
556 applications).
- 557 6. **Volumes:** These are abstractions that allow the storage used by a container to
558 be managed independently of the container. Volumes are made accessible by
559 mounting them in a container.

560 6.1. *Fundamentals*

561 The current implementation opts for a point-to-point communication model (cf.
562 control flow communication medium). It allows for more straightforward and explicit
563 communication between two parties, making it more suitable for the deliberate routing
564 decisions that consider data locality. The gRPC framework is chosen to support the
565 communication between different components. The containers used to perform the
566 steps, inspired from the microservice-oriented architecture, are long-lived, and each can
567 process multiple units of data. This reduces the overhead in performance incurred by
568 creating and deleting containers constantly throughout the execution of a workflow. A
569 clear distinction between different aspects of the communication between components
570 is made:

- 571 1. The components communicating with each other adhere to a particular contract or
572 interface.
- 573 2. The actual execution is handled by the logic implementing the contract/interface.
- 574 3. The communicating parties have to employ compatible serialisation/deserialisation
575 protocols to exchange messages.
- 576 4. The transport aspect encompasses both fundamental mediums (memory, disk,
577 network) and abstractions on top of those (such as the HTTP protocol).

578 By leveraging the long-lived nature of the containers, the proposed implementation
579 also attempts to reuse established connections to remote machines (connection pooling).
580 The TCP protocol requires three network round-trips to perform the three-way hand-
581 shake. If the protocol on top of TCP uses SSL to secure the connections (e.g., HTTPS),
582 more network round-trips are required to negotiate and establish a secure connection. If
583 the connection pooling is not enabled, the time to establish connections increases with
584 the number of connections. For example, if many small data units flow through the
585 system, the time for establishing connections can represent a significant percentage of
586 the total execution time of the workflow. With geographically distributed resources, the
587 performance cost of network round-trips becomes more significant with the increase in
588 the physical distance between hosts, thus making connection pooling even more critical.

589 6.2. Orchestrator

590 A single instance of the orchestrator (Figure 4) is deployed, and it is for all the
591 components in the cluster through a Kubernetes service. The single-replica strategy is
592 needed because the central orchestrator is a stateful service that keeps the state in mem-
593 ory. Setting up a multi-replica orchestrator is beneficial for performance, scalability, and
594 resilience. However, it also requires external solutions to store, share, and synchronise
595 the state among the replicas. A workflow consists of a sequence of processing steps.
596 Each step specifies a name that uniquely identifies the processing logic of the step. The
597 orchestrator uses the names of steps to find pods hosting the specified processing logic
598 through Kubernetes labels. In addition to the name, data source and data sink identifiers
599 are also part of step specification. The data source and sink identify the data storage
600 solutions where the input and output data should be retrieved and stored, respectively.
601 A single workflow can utilise multiple storage solutions, such as Cloud, Edge, and
602 shared storage (cf. data communication medium).

603 Registering and retrieving workflows is done through a service, **workflow defini-**
604 **tion service**, using **workflow definition store** and exposed by the central orchestrator.
605 The orchestrator exposes another service, **orchestration service**, responsible for orches-
606 trating the execution of the workflow registered through the workflow definition service.
607 The execution of the workflow is driven by the availability of data in the system, as
608 opposed to a task-driven execution approach [47]. The orchestrator is responsible for
609 notifying the pods hosting the logic necessary to process the new unit of data according
610 to the workflow definition. The communication between the orchestrator and pods
611 hosting steps is asynchronous with respect to the actual execution of the step. The step
612 pod does not wait for the step execution to finish before returning to the orchestrator.
613 The **work tracker** component stores a mapping between a request and the step executing
614 the request. The orchestrator reads this mapping to determine what is the next step to
615 invoke. In parallel, the work tracker also keeps a counter of active computation requests
616 for each pod. When a request arrives, it is put in a queue. This allows a response to be
617 sent back to the caller without waiting for the finishing of the processing of the data,
618 which can potentially be a long-running operation. The **executor** component retrieves
619 requests from the queue and starts a background thread to process the request, allowing
620 it to process multiple requests in parallel quickly. The **cluster state provider** component,
621 using Kubernetes API Server, provides a list of all the pods in the cluster that can perform
622 the desired processing logic. Finally, the agent extends the central orchestrator and han-
623 dles the orchestration at a local and individual step level. It handles the communication
624 with other components on behalf of the compute step.

625 6.3. Request Routing

626 Request routing discussed earlier is a multi-objective problem. For the proposed
627 implementation, request routing uses the distance and current load as inputs. Data
628 localisation captures information about the host (either storing the data or running a
629 pod) and the zone. The zone is a general term meant to capture groups of hosts near one
630 another. When routing a request through the orchestrator, a unit of data with a specified
631 data localisation must be paired with a pod that can process it, with a potentially different
632 data localisation.

633 One input to the routing decision algorithm is the distance between the localisation
634 of the data to be processed and the localisation of each pod. A large number indicates
635 the data transfer to the pod is likely to take longer. The distance between the same
636 hosts is considered to be zero. For all other cases, the orchestrator constructs a $N \times N$
637 matrix hosting the distances between each of the N zones (assuming there are N zones
638 in total in the system). We presume that the distance between hosts within the same
639 zone is higher than zero but lower than the distance between two different zones. The
640 orchestrator uses the **distance calculator** to calculate the distance (see Figure 4) and the
641 work tracker component to get the number of concurrent requests on each pod.

Figure 4. An overview of the orchestrator component.

642 We propose two flavors of the selection algorithm. The first one is the greedy
 643 approach: (i) the pods with several active connections higher than a configurable number
 644 (three by default) are eliminated, to avoid overloading a particular pod due to the uneven
 645 load balancing introduced by the data locality preferences, (ii) from the remaining pods,
 646 the one with the shortest calculated distance is selected (greedy selection), and (iii) if
 647 no pod remains, the request is added back into the queue to be processed at a later
 648 time. The second approach is slightly modified and focuses more on spreading the
 649 load among the available resources. Instead of always choosing the closest pod, this
 650 variant spreads the load evenly at a zone level and falls back to a different zone when
 651 the load on the pods passes a configurable threshold (three by default). The zone with
 652 available resources closest to where data are stored is chosen. Given seven requests to
 653 route, the order in which each strategy leverages the available resources is presented in
 654 Figure 5. Both algorithms exhibit the valuable characteristic of leveraging the full set of
 655 resources available in the continuum in a prioritised order to reduce the cost and latency
 656 introduced by data transfer while at the same time avoiding overloading a particular set
 657 of pods.

658 6.4. Framework Agent

659 Since the framework agent is logically coupled with a compute step, the two are
 660 always deployed together by leveraging the sidecar deployment pattern [48]. The agent
 661 and the compute step are separated in different containers, and they can communicate
 662 efficiently via local network calls within the host. With pods being the atomic unit

Figure 5. Routing priority for the greedy and load spreading algorithms.

663 Kubernetes can manage, this deployment model guarantees that each pod hosting a
 664 compute step container also contains an agent container.

665 The agents implement a service to expose a communication endpoint for the or-
 666 chestrator. The request from the orchestrator contains the metadata needed by the data
 667 source to find the data the step should process, a unique identifier for the request, and
 668 the identifier of the data adapter to be used as a data sink. Upon receiving the request,
 669 the agent will perform the following operations:

- 670 1. Forward the metadata to the data adapter specified in the request from the orches-
 671 trator.
- 672 2. Once the data adapter ensures that the data are available at a path the compute
 673 step container can access, the compute step is invoked with the path to the file
 674 containing the data it needs to process.
- 675 3. For each output emitted by the compute step, the framework agent will instruct
 676 the sink data adapter to register the output.
- 677 4. Once the sink data adapter returns the metadata necessary to identify the newly
 678 added data, it is sent, together with the initial request, back to the orchestrator to
 679 notify that new data are available.

680 The agent keeps track of the number of concurrent requests being executed, allowing
 681 only a configurable number of requests to be executed in parallel.

682 6.5. Data Adapter

683 In the current implementation, data adapters only work with files (i.e., data re-
 684 trieved from the storage solution is stored in a file, and only uploading data from a file
 685 to the storage solution is supported). Data adapters are deployed using the DaemonSet

686 concept in Kubernetes. One pod for each type of storage adapter is deployed to every
687 node of the Kubernetes cluster. The DaemonSet choice assumes the number of (possibly
688 different) types of storage adapters is limited, and, thus, the overhead of running one
689 pod of each type is negligible. Different storage solutions can be integrated, and the
690 associated adapters can be added to extend the solution's capabilities.

691 The distributed storage system leverages the local storage of every node in the
692 cluster to store the data processed by the workflow. Besides reading and writing data,
693 the interface also captures the localisation information about the data as part of the
694 communication. Hard linking is used to leverage further the advantage provided by
695 data locality. Hard linking is a faster operation than copying, and thus it further reduces
696 the time spent on moving data between directories. The volumes are based on directories
697 in the underlying node file system. Even though different directories are mounted as
698 different volumes in pods, the resolution of hard links is delegated to the node file
699 system. This allows the hard links to cross volumes mounted in different pods. By
700 contrast, symbolic links operate by attempting to resolve a particular path, so they
701 cannot cross different volumes unless all pods mount the same volume under the same
702 path. A **data master** was added as a standalone component to separate data handling
703 from the orchestration components. The data master is responsible for keeping track of
704 the location of files stored in the proposed implementation for the distributed storage.
705 The data master component could potentially be extended to offer more functionalities
706 (e.g., data lineage, sharing the same data across multiple workflows, and others). The
707 data master runs in a single pod in the cluster, made available through a service. The
708 state of the data master is stored in memory.

709 The proposed solution for the distributed storage system only offers basic function-
710 alities and lacks most of the features other alternative solutions provide (for example,
711 data replication and redundancy, security, and resilience to failures). However, in some
712 cases, it is possible that results from the processing steps only need to serve as input
713 for the next step and do not have strict requirements for how the data should be stored.
714 For such cases, the presented solution can be used as the data transfer medium, thus
715 benefiting from an efficient means to fully leverage the data locality functionality. Within
716 a single workflow, it is possible to use multiple storage solutions.

717 6.6. Example Flow

718 An example request flow is depicted in Figure 6. When a request is placed in
719 the queue, the orchestrator is notified about available new data (1). The executor then
720 retrieves the request (2) and starts a background thread to process the request. The first
721 step in the processing is to determine which step should be invoked for the current
722 notification (3), based on the request and the workflow definition. Once the step is
723 determined, the cluster state provider provides all the available pods to perform the
724 required step (4). Based on the current load and distance to the data to be processed, one
725 of the available options is chosen (5), and the request is sent to the appropriate agent (6).

726 Once the agent receives the notification, it sends a request to the correct data adapter,
727 based on the received data (7). If the file is not available locally, the local storage adapter
728 will send a request to the data master (8) to determine where the file that needs to be
729 processed is stored and will then send a request to download the data from the respective
730 peer (9). After (8-9), or if the file is available locally, the local storage data adapter places
731 the data in the volume the compute step can access (10) and responds to request (7).
732 The agent then notifies the compute step that data are available (11), and the compute
733 step reads the data (12), performs the processing logic (13), writes the output to the
734 corresponding volume (14), and responds to the agent with the path to the output data
735 (15). The agent sends a request to the local storage adapter to register the newly available
736 data (16). The local storage adapter moves the new data into the permanent storage
737 folder (17) and notifies the data master about the new data (18). The agent notifies the

Figure 6. An example request flow in detail.

738 orchestrator that new data are available (19), and the process is repeated for all units of
 739 data flowing through the system.

740 7. Evaluation

741 Through a series of experiments, we compare: (i) our approach with Argo Work-
 742 flows in order to analyse the run-time performances, and (ii) different configurations for
 743 the proposed solution with one another, for analysing individual aspects in isolation.
 744 The test environment is set up on the Microsoft Azure Cloud using only Infrastruc-
 745 ture-as-a-Service offerings (virtual machines and networking capabilities). The test environ-
 746 ment is Standard D2s v3 (two vCPUs, 8GB memory) virtual machines, provisioned in three
 747 different Azure regions (EastUS, WestEurope, and NorthEurope) to mimic the geograph-
 748 ical distribution of resources in a real Cloud and Edge topology. One virtual machine
 749 serves as the Kubernetes master node (and did not run additional pods). In addition to
 750 the master node, two virtual machines are configured as Kubernetes worker nodes in

751 each region. The lightweight K3s⁹ distribution of Kubernetes is manually installed on
752 each virtual machine. All machines are part of the same cluster.

753 We use an example workflow to evaluate the architecture and implementation
754 of the systems, which contains four sequential steps, each accepting a file as input,
755 randomly shuffling the bytes, and writing the shuffled result as output. The motivation
756 for choosing an artificial workflow is the ability to capture and describe the behaviour
757 of the solution in terms of universally applicable measures (e.g., bytes for data size).
758 In contrast, a workflow processing particular data types (such as images) captures the
759 specific behaviour better. However, the conclusions are harder to generalise because the
760 data type in specific cases is more restrictive in terms of size and data characteristics.
761 For the first three steps, every machine in the cluster runs one instance of each step
762 type. The final step is run only on machines in the EastUS region, simulating a step that
763 can only run on Cloud instances in a real scenario. Both the central orchestrator and
764 the data master components are deployed on machines in the WestEurope region. Two
765 additional supporting components are used when running the experiments. The load
766 generator is responsible for injecting data into the cluster and notifying the orchestrator
767 when data are available. The load generator creates files containing random bytes and
768 triggers workflows for these files. The size and number of files to be injected into the
769 cluster are configurable. The load generator also supports injecting data into two regions
770 in parallel. The telemetry reader is responsible for gathering data on the execution of
771 the workflow (e.g., time spent in different components, the quantity of data transferred
772 between regions, and load spreading). The data is retrieved using the Jaeger API and is
773 exported to CSV files, which are later analysed through Python/Jupyter notebooks.

774 The choice of the testing environment is motivated by the main focus of the paper
775 that is the impact of data locality on a geographically distributed computing setting.
776 The proposed Cloud setup is capable of creating a geographically distributed system
777 by provisioning virtual machines in different regions and integrating them into a single
778 system. There are key differences from using a real IoT/Edge/Cloud setup, such as
779 hardware heterogeneity (different CPU capabilities and even architectures, I/O through-
780 put, network characteristics). However, to better isolate the benefit of data locality from
781 other factors, the Cloud setup is sufficient, as it reduces the entropy introduced by a real
782 world setup. Changing the experimental setup either at hardware level or any upper
783 level may result in different results, to be demonstrated and discussed further in the
784 following subsections; however, we consider that the conditions simulated in the test
785 setup are sufficiently generic to be applicable to a wide-range of real world scenarios.
786 We address the primary parameters (data size and contention rates) that could influence
787 the benefits introduced by the data locality and leave out the parameters that could play
788 a secondary role.

789 *7.1. Comparison with Argo Workflows*

790 The example workflow presented earlier is run with four different file sizes/counts,
791 both on Argo Workflows and the proposed solution, for comparing run-time perfor-
792 mance. We implement the workflow using the Argo workflow definition language. The
793 data communication medium between the steps is Cloud storage (Azure BlobStorage),
794 with one instance provisioned per region. The steps can read input data from any region
795 but write output data to the region they are running in (e.g., a step in WestEurope
796 can retrieve data from NorthEurope, but it always writes the output to WestEurope).
797 Argo orchestration components (e.g., Argo Server) are deployed to worker nodes in the
798 WestEurope region, similar to the proposed implementation.

799 Files of different sizes are uploaded manually to the Cloud storage in WestEurope
800 and NorthEurope region, and workflows are triggered from a client running outside the
801 cluster, with these files as inputs. In terms of data locality, we evaluate two different

⁹ <https://k3s.io>

Figure 7. Performance comparison between the proposed solution and Argo Workflows.

802 approaches. First, no data locality is captured in the workflow definition, allowing the
 803 steps to be assigned to nodes anywhere in the cluster. Second, using the node selectors
 804 to limit where step pods are instantiated, the processing is kept within the same region
 805 (e.g., files originating from WestEurope were to be processed in WestEurope as much
 806 as possible). By default, the orchestration component of Argo reacts to changes in step
 807 states (e.g., a step has finished) once every 10 seconds. This default value is unsuitable
 808 for workflows processing small amounts of data quickly, and for these experiments,
 809 we change it to one second, which is the minimum recommended value. The exact
 810 configuration used to deploy Argo Workflows for the experiment is available in the
 811 GitHub repository of the solution.

812 Figure 7 presents the average running time of a workflow, given different data sizes
 813 and numbers of files processed in parallel. The X-axis denotes the number of files used
 814 in each of the two Edge regions, WestEurope and NorthEurope, along with their size.
 815 For example, “3 files, 1MB” indicates that three files of 1MB each are passed through
 816 the workflow from both WestEurope and NorthEurope in parallel (six files in total). The
 817 Y-axis is the time spent on the execution of the workflow, measured in milliseconds. The
 818 numbers on the Y-axis are averaged from several iterations. The results show a low
 819 variance between different iterations. The chart compares the numbers from four runs
 820 of the same workflow: (i) in Argo, both with region-level data locality and without data
 821 locality, and (ii) in our solution, with the two flavors of the routing algorithm, greedy
 822 and load spreading.

823 From experiments, we can observe the following:

- 824 1. In the case of processing small data chunks that take little time to process, the
 825 proposed solution outperformed Argo Workflows by a factor of five.
- 826 2. As the data size grows, the time spent on executing the logic of the step increases,
 827 and the benefit of data locality reduces.
- 828 3. Data from the second case (three files, 10MB) show that using data locality does
 829 not affect the case of Argo Workflows. Furthermore, in the fourth case (three
 830 files, 100MB), using data locality in the workflow has a detrimental effect on
 831 performance.
- 832 4. The solutions that leverage data locality attempt to perform the work close to
 833 the data, while the other solutions spread the load evenly across the available

- 834 machines. The gathered telemetry indicates that the steps of the example workflow
 835 are significantly slower when multiple instances are scheduled on the same host,
 836 as they are competing for resources.
- 837 5. Considering that there are two worker nodes available in each region, processing
 838 three files in parallel results in at least two of the files to be processed on the same
 839 node when data locality is enabled. This load distribution significantly offsets the
 840 reduction in data transfer time.
 - 841 6. When processing only two files of data sizes of 10MB and 100MB, the load can be
 842 better spread on the testbed topology (two files can be processed in parallel on the
 843 two host machines available in each region), and the benefit of data locality can be
 844 observed.
 - 845 7. On all cases, however, our proposed solution with the load spreading algorithm
 846 proves faster to execute the example workflow. However, the benefits vary, de-
 847 pending on the data size, from 500% (for the three files, 1MB) to roughly 20% (for
 848 the two files, 100MB case).

849 7.2. Evaluation under Different Configurations

850 A series of experiments are run with different configurations of the proposed
 851 solution to understand better the effect and behaviour of particular aspects in isolation.
 852 The time spent during the execution of the workflows is split into three categories:

- 853 (i) **Data** is referring to the time spent handling the necessary data movement
 854 (downloading the input data for a step, uploading the outputs, and moving
 855 data between directories on the node file system).
- 856 (ii) **Compute** is referring to the time spent executing the logic of the processing
 857 step.
- 858 (iii) **Control** is referring to the time spent in the orchestration component and calcu-
 859 lated as a difference between the total execution time of a step measured by the
 860 orchestrator and the time spent on the other two categories.

861 Optimising individual areas does not always translate into significant improve-
 862 ments in end-to-end performance. In some cases, optimisations in one area may degrade
 863 performance for the other areas. In the example workflow, most of the time is spent on
 864 the compute category, especially on larger data sizes. A different step implementation,
 865 which only reads the input and writes it to the output directly (echo functionality), is
 866 used for the following experiments. Under the same conditions, the two implemen-
 867 tations cause a significant difference in the distribution of time. Figure 8 presents the
 868 distribution of where time is spent on average for a single-step processing 10 MB of data
 869 and showcases the significant difference between the two-step implementations.

Figure 8. Time distribution for same workflow, but different steps: echo (left) and byte shuffle (right).

870 Regarding data handling, we analyse locality-aware routing, hard linking, and
871 load spreading across the Computing Continuum. To study the effect of the locality-
872 aware scheduling in isolation, a configuration allowing the orchestrator to skip the
873 locality-aware routing and rely instead on reaching individual step instances through a
874 Kubernetes service is used. By default, Kubernetes services use a round-robin routing
875 algorithm, thus spreading the requests between all available instances, regardless of their
876 physical localisation. Figure 9 shows a significant difference in average time spent for
877 transferring data between machines, with data locality significantly reducing the time
878 spent. The X-axis represents three different experiments. We pass files of 1MB, 10 MB,
879 100 MB through the workflow, respectively. These sizes are reasonable when taking into
880 account the scale of IoT / Edge setups. For example, given 1000 devices generating 100
881 MB per minute each, it suddenly becomes 100 Gb per minute in the entire system. The
882 Y-axis represents the average time spent on moving data (in milliseconds). We observe
883 that the more routing decisions in data are transferred over more considerable distances
884 (e.g., from WestEurope to EastUS), the higher the step's overall execution time. This
885 implies that data locality is more beneficial for systems spread over more expansive
886 areas.

887 An experiment comparing the performance of hard linking against the copying data
888 indicated that hard linking executes in constant time. In contrast, time spent copying
889 data increases with the size of the data. However, the performance benefit is negligible
890 at the end, especially under the assumption that the size of the data directly influences
891 the execution time of the processing step. For load spreading across a Computing
892 Continuum, tuning the example workflow with configurations where data is produced
893 in a single zone at increasing rates showed that the proposed solution spreads the load
894 across the available resources. Prioritising step instances, in the order of host storing
895 the data, host in the same zone as the host storing the data, host in the next closest zone,
896 and host in the EastUS zone, results in bandwidth utilisation savings, especially for
897 cases when the data locality information captures the exact host storing the data. The
898 greedy solution is more likely to perform better when it comes to bandwidth savings, as
899 it weighs data locality higher than the load spreading. However, it may perform poorly
900 in terms of execution time for resource-intensive cases, as presented in experiments with
901 Argo Workflows.

Data locality on and Data locality off

Figure 9. Average time spent on transferring data with and without data locality.

902 Regarding the control time, we focus on long-lived containers and connection re-use.
903 The significant difference between Argo and the proposed solution in the cases where
904 small and frequent data units need to be processed is due to the overhead introduced
905 by Argo using ephemeral containers. Apart from the cost of instantiating the container,
906 observations made during the experimentation indicate that a significant portion of the
907 time is spent starting up the application after the container is created. This observation
908 is made because the first run of a workflow after deploying the Kubernetes cluster was
909 significantly slower than any subsequent run. For the example workflow, with three
910 files of 1 MB each as input, the first run took roughly 18 seconds while the subsequent
911 runs took around 5 seconds.

912 We compare two configurations of the agent to measure the effect of connection
913 re-use in the agent component: (i) in the first configuration, the connection re-use is not
914 enabled; thus, a new connection for each message to be transmitted should be created,
915 and (ii) in the second configuration, a single connection is re-used for all the messages.
916 The observations indicate that while there is a performance gain in isolation (on average,
917 30 milliseconds per message for the first case and 10 milliseconds per message on the
918 second case), the impact is not noticeable on the end to end latencies for the considered
919 data sizes. However, more frequent events and lower data sizes could potentially make
920 connection pooling a relevant optimisation.

921 The observations made throughout the experiments indicate that there are several
922 variables on which the benefit of the proposed approach depends:

- 923 1. The nature of the processing steps: The resource contention caused by multiple
924 steps running on the same machine can influence the routing algorithm's optimal
925 configuration controlling the balance between load spreading and data locality.
- 926 2. Distance and connection speed between the resources: A topology spreading over
927 a wider area benefits more for the data locality-aware routing.
- 928 3. Frequency and processing duration of events: The biggest improvement is obtained
929 by leveraging long-lived containers for frequent and small events.

930 8. Conclusion

931 This article proposed a novel architecture and a proof-of-concept implementation
932 for container-centric Big Data workflow orchestration systems. Our proposed solution
933 enables the orchestration components to consider data locality, quantified using a flexible
934 model that accounts for the physical distance between hosts spread across the Computing
935 Continuum. Our solution is better suited for processing small and frequent data units
936 by leveraging long-lived containers re-used to process multiple units. Furthermore, it
937 extends the ideas behind isolating processing steps in separate containers to address the
938 data management aspect of Big Data workflows. As such, the logic needed to interact
939 with data management systems is encapsulated in containers, providing the same
940 benefits as for processing logic (technology agnostic solution, isolation, and lightweight).
941 The communication between components is enabled by an efficient and contract-based
942 remote procedure call framework. Finally, a set of experiments are executed to compare
943 the proposed solution against Argo Workflows and to study individual aspects in
944 isolation.

945 Overall, the proposed solution improved the performance and reduced bandwidth
946 usage for container-centric Big Data workflows while maintaining a good separation
947 of concerns and reducing complexity for the framework's users. The optimisations
948 proved the solution better suited for environments where Cloud and Edge resources are
949 leveraged together. Separating the interaction with data in a dedicated component, thus
950 advancing toward a better separation of concerns, also facilitated the implementation of
951 data locality as a built-in feature of the framework. This further proves the usefulness of
952 creating small and isolated components in a distributed system. The proposed solution is
953 far from feature-parity with the other existing solutions. However, it highlights potential
954 areas of improvement that do not deviate significantly from the fundamentals of the

955 existing architectures, making it possible to integrate the presented ideas and findings
 956 into them. While limited in scope, the conducted experiments are representative of the
 957 challenges the solution attempts to address. The experiments also highlighted that the
 958 benefit provided by the solution could vary significantly based on different factors. The
 959 instrumentation provided with the software solution can facilitate the same kind of
 960 performance analysis under the conditions relevant for each use case.

961 Future work includes extending the solution in multiple directions: (i) Simple
 962 workflow definitions were supported in the current approach to investigate potential
 963 performance improvements, but most real use cases require complex constructs. In this
 964 context, a few examples include supporting direct acyclic graph-structured workflows,
 965 processing steps to receive input from more than one data source, and supporting
 966 aggregation over multiple data units. (ii) Both data and processing logic are isolated in
 967 different components, and the workflow definition language uses these components as
 968 building blocks. A potential direction is creating a marketplace-like ecosystem where
 969 data and processing logic are exchanged between parties in the form of such components.
 970 (iii) A central piece of the proposed solution is the routing algorithm that considers load
 971 and data locality. Further improving the heuristic and adding more dimensions (such as
 972 matching node capabilities) can lead to better results. (iv) The solution could be extended
 973 to support stream processing; in addition, avoiding using a disk to transfer the data to
 974 be processed is also desirable in such cases. (v) Finally, there are two possible scaling
 975 bottlenecks in the proposal. First, the platform could benefit from creating and deleting
 976 processing steps dynamically to meet the current demands. Second, the orchestrator
 977 and the data master components are single instance applications, becoming a bottleneck
 978 under a high load and needing horizontal scaling.

979 **Author Contributions:** Funding acquisition, D.R., N.N., M.M.; supervision, D.R., N.N., A.S,
 980 M.M., A.H.P.; conceptualisation, A.A.C, N.N., A.Q.K., A.S., M.M, D.R.; Methodology, all; Software,
 981 A.A.C.; investigation, A.A.C., N.N., A.Q.K.; Writing - original draft, all; Writing - review & editing,
 982 all. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

983 **Funding:** The work in this paper was partly funded by the EC H2020 project “DataCloud” (grant
 984 number 101016835) and the NFR project “BigDataMine” (grant number 309691).

985 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

986 Abbreviations

987 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

988	DAG	Directed acyclic graph
	HDFS	Hadoop file system
989	IoT	Internet of things
	RDMA	Remote direct memory access

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